

Movement Event Agreements

This event is a firm container event, meaning that safety, harmoniousness, and self expression are safeguarded through a handful of explicit expectations. These expectations center around what we are not going to do.

1. **Non-violent.** Actions or language of violence, aggression, intolerance, and discrimination are unwelcome here. Playfighting, martial explorations or demonstrations, and sparring are included in this category.
2. **Non-coercive.** Actions or language that intend to cause another to move, act, or think in a certain way through the use of force are unwelcome here. Lifting another person without regard for their volition is included in this category.
3. **Non-erotic.** Actions or language that explicitly explore eroticism, or that attempt to generate sexual excitement in oneself or others, are unwelcome here.

These agreements are proposed because there is a wide variety of opinions about what movement events should or should not encompass. Experience shows that many cases of misunderstanding, injury, and other troubles arise from such differences.

Please note that there is no judgement implied about these few explorations that are not to be undertaken here, nor is there a judgement about events that choose to permit or encourage them. It is simply the choice made here in an attempt to ensure safety.

There are also expectations for suitable attire. Nudity or partial nudity, externally worn underwear, and tights are all considered unsuitable for this event, as are clothes with exposed metal, large rips, or dangling cords. Natural fibers are preferred.

Finally, participants are expected to respect the fact that decision-making capacity for the structure, management, and stewardship of this event rests solely with the organizers.

These expectations are to be clearly expressed at the time the event is announced, and potential participants are asked to read and agree to them prior to paying or signing up.

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Movement Events Agreements v. 2 License

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